

COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS AN APPROACH TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORKING ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The pedagogical possibilities for developing students' independent work activities based on a competency-based approach have been improved based on the clarification of the stages of didactic organizational-managerial, psychological-pedagogical and cultural approaches, the organization of independent activity, and the use of innovative technologies in the information educational environment.*

Keywords: *competence, independent work, pedagogy, didactic, psychological and pedagogical, innovative activity, information, education.*

INTRODUCTION

Independent work activities perform didactic functions, such as attracting students to their profession, expanding their knowledge, cultivating and activating their sense of responsibility, and developing their ability to think independently. As noted in experiments, if the training is conducted in a typical listening-only method, students absorb at most 15-20 percent of the information, while when modern technologies are used, this figure has been confirmed to increase to 85-90 percent. The effectiveness of non-traditional education also lies in the fact that its participants acquire holistic, systematic knowledge and, based on the development of independent and creative thinking skills, form basic skills for future professional activities, ensuring a direct connection of the educational process with practice. That is why it is considered one of the highly effective methods of developmental teaching. The initiative and skills of teachers are also important in organizing students' independent work activities outside the classroom. Software education and software tools based on modern pedagogical technologies, innovative technologies are the future of today's education. Therefore, the creation of an innovative learning environment is associated with the digitalization of educational processes [1,2].

The theoretical basis of scientific works on the problems of organizing students' independent work activities, preparing them for subjects, and pedagogical approaches to organizing independent work activities, as well as its current state, were studied, local and foreign scientific, pedagogical, methodological literature and regulatory documents on the problem under study were studied and analyzed, and goals and objectives were determined.

Independent work is an activity carried out in the process of self-development, acquisition of professional skills, accumulation of knowledge that encourages the student to perform independent work with a creative approach, formation of practical skills, and critical thinking in curricular and extracurricular activities [3,4].

The literature review showed that many scholars have partially expressed their views and opinions on "Independent Work Activity". That is, some scholars have expressed their views and opinions on "Independent Work" and "Critical Thinking", some have expressed their views and opinions on "Professional" and "Practical" skills, but no scholar has fully studied "Independent Work Activity".

Figure 1. Model for organizing independent work activities of students

The implementation of complex approaches to the activity of independent work is carried out through the creation of software.

In organizing students' independent work activities: "Independent work" plays a key role. Considering the various expressions of the concept of "independent work", we can say that in the pedagogical dictionary, independent work of students includes "a wide variety of educational activities carried out without the direct participation of the teacher". In the above interpretations of independent work, it is precise that the "student's performance of tasks without the direct participation of the teacher" serves as the main characteristic that characterizes it as a form of learning. Due to this characteristic, independent work stands out among other organizational forms of educational activity[5,6,7].

It is also important to develop critical thinking skills in organizing students' independent work activities. Critical thinking is a special type of thinking that draws conclusions by analyzing facts. This concept is complex and has various definitions, including rationality, skepticism, objective analysis, and fact-checking. Critical thinking is a form of thinking that is self-directed, self-disciplined, self-controlled, and self-correcting. It requires accepting and applying rigorous standards of mindfulness. Critical thinking requires mastering effective communication and problem-solving skills, as well as overcoming our inherent egocentrism and sociocentrism. In organizing students' independent work activities, it is important for students to acquire professional and practical skills.

We know that today, in the international development system, education is recognized as a key factor ensuring sustainable development in our century, and the concept established until 2030 at the International Education Forum held in the Republic of Korea noted the relevance of "creating opportunities for quality education throughout life". This, in turn, expanded the opportunity to create an educational and methodological support for the professional training system for future teachers, using educational technologies aimed at developing independent thinking and creative thinking, and creativity, to acquire and develop professional skills in students, organize professional and practical training of students based on an innovative approach. In the context of the informatization of the world's education system, scientific research is being conducted to update the educational and methodological support for the development of professional skills of future personnel based on international requirements, and to clarify the psychological and pedagogical factors of the development of students' professional skills. In

solving these tasks, it is important to develop methodological resources for the development of professional skills and improve them based on an innovative approach, create pedagogical conditions, and use modern educational technologies to improve the quality and efficiency of teaching.

Independent work of students is not just an important form of the educational process, it must become the basis of this process. In this regard, the issues of ensuring the stimulation of independent cognitive activity of students require special attention. Attention is paid to the formation of learning motivation, which is undoubtedly the driving force of education [7,8].

The term competence is derived from the Latin word "competere", which means "I am able, worthy" and indicates awareness, knowledge, and experience in a certain field (UzME, 2002).

One of the main tasks of higher education is to form a creative personality of a specialist capable of independent work, independent development, and innovative activity of students based on a competency-based approach. This problem can only be solved by moving from a teaching paradigm to an education paradigm. This is what the reform of higher education that is being implemented today is all about.

It is necessary to transform the student from an inactive consumer of knowledge into an active creator who is able to plan and predict their independent work, show initiative, express a problem, analyze ways to solve it, obtain an optimal result, and prove its correctness.

The introduction of a competency-based approach to the higher education system requires significant changes in the goals, content, form of education, teaching methods, pedagogical technologies, control methods, and the relationship between educators and learners. In particular, in the "knowledgeable" approach, the goal of education is to develop knowledge, skills, and competencies in each subject in the learner, while in the "competency-based" approach, the goal is to develop integrated knowledge, skills, and competencies in the learner across subjects. Accordingly, it is envisaged to change the content of lectures, practical classes, seminars, and laboratory classes, which are the existing forms of organizing education in higher education institutions. It is advisable that lecture classes be in the form of problem-based learning, seminar classes should be aimed at developing creative thinking, and practical exercises should be aimed at developing research skills. In organizing independent work, individuality should be emphasized and they should be more in volume.

Then, it is necessary to gradually move from a knowledge-based approach to a competency-based approach, and in this process, the implementation of algorithms by students, the "forced" acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, and the control of the entire process of the student's independent work gradually replace (change to) the independent acquisition of the necessary knowledge and skills by the student, independent control and independent assessment of his own knowledge, and control of the direct result of the student's independent activity by the teacher. Thus, it is inevitable that a competency-based approach to organizing independent work at the end of a student's education at a higher educational institution will be a priority. This will help develop in the student the qualities that will allow him to independently master professional knowledge and relevant functional skills when necessary [7,8].

Thus, today, the organization of independent work of students based on a competency-based approach occupies a worthy place in the system of organizing the higher education process.

The organization of independent work of students is one of the most urgent problems of the modern stage of education. It is associated with the systematic acquisition of new knowledge,

which is the basis for the formation of cognitive independence, which is necessary for the professional formation of the teacher's personality. Analysis of some studies shows that insufficient attention is paid to solving the problem of organizing students' independent work. Its complexity and multifactorial nature indicate that it is very difficult to solve this problem using traditional forms of education. Thus, the actualization of independent acquisition of new knowledge is associated with the existence of a contradiction in the modern education system, which, on the one hand, consists in the need to acquire knowledge quickly, and on the other hand, is associated with the limited possibilities of assimilation of knowledge by the subject of education and acquisition of new knowledge using traditional teaching methods.

In our opinion, the organization of independent work during the development of the main educational program of students in a higher education institution should be carried out in conditions of integration of knowledge-based and competency-based approaches.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the main goal of involving students in independent learning and teaching them to actively acquire independent knowledge is to teach them to think independently, ensuring that they increase and update their knowledge by acquiring new knowledge based on the needs of the time, not only during their student years, but also in their subsequent professional activities, to develop their creative thinking, to increase their ability to draw correct conclusions as a result of the ability to sort the necessary information in a vast information space, and, as a result, to make a significant contribution to the development of our country and the well-being of our people by producing high-quality people and high-quality personnel for society.

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